

Optimizing PV Self-Consumption through Electric Water Heater Modeling and Scheduling

M. Heleno, D. Rua, C. Gouveia,
A. Madureira
INESC TEC
Centre for Power and Energy Systems
Porto, Portugal
{mdheleno, drua, cgouveia,
amadureira}@inescporto.pt

M. A. Matos, J. P. Lopes
INESC TEC and Faculty of
Engineering of the University of Porto
Porto, Portugal
{mam, jpl}@fe.up.pt

Nuno Silva, Sérgio Salustio
Bosch Thermotechnology
Aveiro, Portugal
{nunoandre.silva
sergio.salustio}@pt.bosch.com

Abstract— This paper aims at presenting a Home Energy Management System (HEMS) module capable of scheduling electric water heater (EWH) appliances in order to optimize the PV self-consumption. A multi-period optimization model is presented. Laboratory tests were conducted to validate the model and to demonstrate the capability of this HEMS module to address recent challenges of self-consumption in a domestic environment. A commercial EWH device developed by Bosch communicating with the HEMS module is used to perform the tests.

I. INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic (PV) self-consumption is being adopted in Europe with the objective of promoting increase of renewable generation, energy efficiency with concerns on avoiding grid problems, such as voltage rise during PV generation peak periods [1]. In some countries (*e.g.*, Belgium, Denmark and the Netherlands) PV self-consumption measures encompass net metering schemes aiming at balancing endogenous generation and local consumption for large time periods. In contrast, in countries like Germany and Portugal, a new policy is being implemented to encourage instantaneous consumption. For instance, the recent Portuguese legislation for small PV installations announces lower remuneration for PV energy fed into the grid in comparison with the retailing energy price for the consumption, thus ending the high feed-in tariffs that were in use [2]. This makes self-consumption always more profitable than injecting PV generation into the grid.

However, daily profiles of PV generation are usually not correlated with the consumption, namely in the residential sector, since a significant part of the population is not at home during daylight hours. Therefore, some form of flexible consumption is required at the local level so that it can be shifted to the periods when PV generation is higher. Battery storage systems have been presented as a solution for matching consumption with PV generation [3] but, in most cases, this type of installation represents an additional cost that will affect the rate of return of PV investments.

Alternative flexibility resources within the domestic environment, such as appliances' load management, can be used to force this correlation between consumption and PV generation. Recently, particular attention has been paid to the Thermostatically Controlled Loads (TCL), namely space heating and electrical hot water systems in the context of PV self-consumption [4]. For instance, Sossan *et al.* [5] proposed a Model Predictive Control (MPC) for scheduling Electric Water Heaters (EWH) consumption with the objective of following PV generation.

This paper introduces a Home Energy Management System (HEMS) module capable of scheduling EWH appliances in order to optimize the PV self-consumption. A multi-period optimization model considering the PV generation forecasts as well as inflexible load is presented. This HEMS module is based on the flexibility estimation methods for TCL [6] and comprises three main functional requirements: Automatic learning of EWH thermal parameters; optimal scheduling for the day-ahead; and of set-point signals to the EWH. Although the method proposed can also be applied to other time frames, in this paper the day-ahead scheduling (performed in the last hour of the previous day) is explored.

Laboratory tests will demonstrate the capability of this HEMS module to address recent challenges of self-consumption in the domestic environment. A EWH device communicating with the HEMS module developed by Bosch is used to perform these tests. A case study comprising 100 EWH will demonstrate the capability of these appliances to accomplish with self-consumption needs.

The paper is organized as follows: section II presents the general framework of the HEMS module for PV self-consumption including procedures for automatic learning of EWH thermal parameters; section III presents the formulation of the optimization problem for the day-ahead scheduling of the EWH consumption; section IV focus on the laboratory demonstration; section V presents the case study that simulates the effect of 100 EWH using the presented

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Fig.1. HEMS module for PV self-consumption.

optimization model; and section VI derives the main conclusions from the work performed.

II. HEMS MODULE FOR PV SELF-CONSUMPTION

The HEMS is a technical platform installed inside the home with the capability of establishing a bidirectional communication with appliances as well as integrating home automation functions. It centralizes information from appliances at the home level, thus allowing Demand Response (DR) in the domestic sector [7]. The HEMS collects real-time information regarding appliances operation [8], namely residential TCL which have a significant potential for load shifting. This characteristic allows the load management systems to achieve energy savings [9] or even more ambitious targets, such as the response to dynamic retail pricing [10] and the participation in the provision of ancillary services [11].

A. HEMS Module for PV self-consumption

The HEMS Module for PV self-consumption shown in Fig. 1, is composed of four main blocks: the scheduling unit, the microgeneration unit, the appliances unit and the consumer interface.

The scheduling unit is the main block of this system and is responsible for calculating the optimal scheduling of the EWH consumption for the day-ahead, taking into account the local forecasts of PV generation, as well as the EWH temperature limits. This unit should ensure that the temperature inside the EWH tank is kept within the maximum and minimum limits. Usually, the maximum temperature is imposed by the security limits of the device whereas the minimum temperature is related to the comfort of the end-user and, hence, it is specified in the consumer interface.

The microgeneration unit collects data on real-time PV generation and can access local forecasts for sun irradiance from 3 days to 1 day-ahead provided by external online services [12]. The appliances unit allows interoperability with the existing controlling systems of the EWH devices. This unit receives real time values of the inside temperature of the EWH tank and performs an on/off control by sending temperature set-point signals to the appliance. Finally, the consumer interface gathers information concerning end-user habits and comfort patterns. In the specific case of the EWH end-users can define their typical hot water consumption and the minimum comfort temperature admissible for hot water usage.

B. Automatic learning of EWH thermal parameters

In order to keep the temperature within the maximum and minimum limits, the scheduling unit should be capable of estimating the water temperature evolution inside the EWH tank for the day-ahead. Usually, Physically-Based Load Models (PBLM), such as the one presented in (1) [13] are widely used to perform a discrete temperature estimation considering a specific time step (Δt):

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + \frac{\Delta t}{C} \left[-\alpha (\theta_{t-1} - \theta_{et}) - v_t (\theta_d - \theta_t) + P_{EWHt} \right] \quad (1)$$

where θ_{et} is the house temperature and $v(t)$ represents the hot water demand by the end user. θ_d is the temperature desired for hot water usage and θ_t is the inlet water temperature. The house temperature (θ_{et}) and the inlet temperature (θ_d) can be easily estimated by the HEMS while $v(t)$ and θ_d are defined by the end-user in the HEMS interface or can be calculated based on historical data of hot water consumption (which is out of the scope of this paper).

C and α represent the thermal capacity and the thermal losses coefficient, respectively. These parameters depend mainly on constructive characteristics of the EWH and are not directly available in the installation guides provided by the appliances manufacturers. Therefore, in real cases the HEMS scheduling unit should be capable of learning autonomously these parameters from the power consumption and temperatures behavior.

The method used to estimate C and α is based on a set of temperature readings from the EWH tank during its regular operation. When the EWH is off, P_{EWH} disappears from the equation – see (1) – and the temperature decreases ($\Delta\theta_{down}$) inside the tank. By reading the temperature before and after the temperature decreasing time (Δt_{down}) it is possible to write α as a function of C :

$$\alpha = -\frac{\Delta\theta_{down}}{\Delta t_{down} \times \Delta\theta_{e_{down}}} C \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\theta_{e_{down}}$ is the average difference between the temperature inside the tank and the ambient temperature.

Similarly, when the EWH state is on, the value of P_{EWH} is equal to the nominal power of the appliance and the temperature increases inside the tank ($\Delta\theta_{up}$). By reading the

temperature before and after the heating time (Δt_{up}) it is possible to write C as a function of α . By replacing α using equation 2, C can be obtained by:

$$C = \frac{\Delta t_{up} \times P_{EWH}}{\Delta \theta_{up} - \frac{\Delta t_{up}}{\Delta t_{down}} \frac{\Delta \theta e_{up}}{\Delta \theta e_{down}} \Delta \theta_{down}} \quad (3)$$

Thus, from (2) and (3) it is possible to find the EWH thermal parameters using only four temperature readings (two during the heating period and the two during the thermal losses period).

III. SCHEDULING EWH CONSUMPTION FOR PV SELF-CONSUMPTION

The optimal scheduling of the EWH for the day-ahead involves solving a multi-period optimization problem. The objective function presented in (4) consists in maximizing the remuneration associated with PV self-consumption for the day-ahead operation taking into account the expected PV generation and the domestic inflexible load.

According to recent Portuguese legislation to promote self-consumption [2], if the sum of uncontrollable residential load (P_{UL}) and the EWH consumption (P_{EWHt}) is lower than the PV generation (P_{PV}), the end-user is remunerated by the energy that is injected into the grid (λ_{PV}). In contrast, if the load is higher than the PV, the end-user has to pay an energy price (λ_E) for the energy consumed that is not locally generated. Since the prices for producing energy from PV are lower than grid delivered the energy prices, self-consumption is always more profitable than injecting PV generation into the grid.

The EWH on/off states in each time period (P_{EWHt}) are the decision variables whereas the maximum and minimum temperatures limits are the constraints of the problem. The EWH temperature θ_t is calculated through the PBLM presented in the previous section.

$$\max \sum_{t=1}^n R_t \quad (4)$$

$$R_t = \begin{cases} \lambda_{PVt} (P_{PVt} - P_{ULt} - P_{EWHt}), & \text{if } P_{PVt} > (P_{ULt} + P_{EWHt}) \\ \lambda_{Et} (P_{PVt} - P_{ULt} - P_{EWHt}), & \text{if } P_{PVt} < (P_{ULt} + P_{EWHt}) \end{cases}$$

Subj. to:

$$\theta_t \geq \theta_{mint} \quad (5)$$

$$\theta_t \leq \theta_{maxt} \quad (6)$$

Equations (4)-(6) describe multi-period optimization problem that leads to the optimum consumption of water heating devices (P_{EWHt}). However, since this consumption is based on/off control, the problem has to include binary decision variables. Therefore, the computational capacity required at the HEMS scheduling unit to run this optimization problem may be significant, especially in situation that involve

large number of periods. For example, the computation of an optimum PV self-consumption for the day-ahead considering 15 minutes time step result in 96 periods for the 24 hours. That means 96 decision variables and 192 constraints.

Furthermore, the computational burden is even more demanding since the objective function (4) is formulated in two branches, which does not allow the direct application of Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) techniques.

Thus, in this section, a linearization of the optimization problem is proposed so that MILP techniques can be applied to solve it while reducing the computational effort of the HEMS.

The transformation of objective function is presented in (7)-(10). Decision variables ψ_t^+ and ψ_t^- were included in order to represent the positive and the negative differences between the PV generation and the consumption ($P_{UL} + P_{EWH}$). The decision binary variable y_t and the large positive constant M are used in (9) and (10) in order to impose an either/or constraint to represent the EWH on/off states.

$$\max \lambda_{PVt} \psi_t^+ - \lambda_{Et} \psi_t^- \quad (7)$$

Subj. to:

$$\psi_t^+ - \psi_t^- = P_{PVt} - P_{ULt} - P_{EWHt} \quad (8)$$

$$\psi_t^+ \leq y_t M \quad (9)$$

$$\psi_t^- \leq (1 - y_t) M \quad (10)$$

As discussed above, the maximum and minimum temperatures are obtained by the PBLM shown in (1). However, this model contains recurrence relations between the decisions variables (P_{EWHt}), *i.e.*, the consumption in each period depends on the consumption in previous periods. For n periods, the maximum and minimum temperature constraints can be presented through a linear matrix inequality in the form $Ax < b$ and $Ax > b$. Equation (11) presents the example of the upper bound temperature limit. The elements a_{kt} of the matrix represent the influence of period k on the consumption of period t as seen in (12). Since k is a period from the past, A becomes a lower triangular matrix. A and b are obtained by replacing θ_t in (5) and (6) by (1). Hence, as shown in (13), the temperature constraint in each period is written as function of the temperature in the first period (θ_0).

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & a_{kt} & \dots \\ a_{1n} & a_{2n} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P_{MC1} \\ P_{MC2} \\ \dots \\ P_{MCn} \end{bmatrix} \leq \begin{bmatrix} b_{max1} \\ b_{max2} \\ \dots \\ b_{maxn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Where:

$$a_{kt} = \begin{cases} \left(1 - \alpha \frac{\Delta t}{C}\right)^{t-k}, & \forall t \geq i \\ 0, & \forall t < i \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

$$b_{mint} = \frac{C}{\Delta t} \theta_{mint} + \sum_{j=1}^t \left[\left(1 - \alpha \frac{\Delta t}{C} \right)^{t-j} \left(-\alpha \theta_{e_j} + v_j (\theta_{d_j} - \theta_{i_j}) \right) \right] + \left(\alpha - \frac{C}{\Delta t} \right) \left(1 - \alpha \frac{\Delta t}{C} \right)^{t-1} \theta_0 \quad (13)$$

IV. LABORATORY TEST CASE

Laboratory tests were conducted to validate the methodology proposed in section II regarding the automatic learning of EWH thermal parameters as well as the optimal day-ahead scheduling model presented in section III.

The tests were divided into three phases: (1) automatic learning of EWH thermal parameters; (2) day-ahead scheduling of EWH consumption taking into account the local forecasts of PV generation, the hot water consumption and the thermal parameters obtained in the first phase; (3) evaluation of the real temperature inside the tank that results from the on/off control profile suggested by the scheduling module.

A. Experimental setup

The tests were conducted at INESC Porto laboratorial facilities [14], where a 1.5 kW EWH developed by Bosch is connected to a 230 V bus as well as a 3 kW PV inverter prototype developed in-house. The EWH allows the report of the temperature inside the tank in a periodic basis using wireless communications. Three hot water uses for shower (35 liters per use at 38°C) were considered: at 7:45, 17:45 and 21:15. The ambient temperature in the laboratory was kept around the 20°C and the measured water inlet temperature was 16.9°C.

In order to emulate a Home Area Network (HAN), a gateway node associated with the HEM was used to remotely exchange data with the EWH, using a proprietary Bosch wireless module. Besides this HAN, the laboratory also includes a certified data acquisition and control system responsible for the automatic metering and logging of data that allows a detailed analysis of the experimental results.

B. Automatic learning of thermal parameters

Thermal parameters of the EWH were calculated considering the temperature readings obtained during the regular operation of the appliance. As described in section II.B, the HEMS performed two tests in order to obtain the thermal admittance (α) and the thermal capacity (C) of the water tank.

During the heating test (73 minutes), the temperature increased from 23.5°C to 46.6°C. Afterwards, the EWH remained disconnected during almost 17 hours. The temperature decreased from 46.6°C to 37.7°C.

Table I summarizes the tests and presents the EWH thermal capacity and thermal loss coefficient obtained by applying the equations shown in (2) and (3).

Table I. EWH thermal capacity and thermal loss coefficient.

		C (kWh/°C)	α (kW/°C)
Heating test			
$\Delta\Theta$ up (°C)		23.10	0.0766
ΔT up (h)		1.22	
PEWH		1.48	
$\Delta\Theta_e$ up (°C)		11.89	
Thermal loss test			
$\Delta\Theta$ dw (°C)		-8.90	1.85E-03
ΔT dw (h)		16.62	
$\Delta\Theta_e$ dw (°C)		22.15	

C. Optimal Scheduling

The EWH optimal scheduling was conducted considering the day-ahead forecasts regarding the PV unit installed at INESC Porto's laboratory. The method presented in section III was used in order to identify the optimal consumption profile of the Bosch EWH for the day ahead, considering 15 minutes time step. Constant energy prices (0.15€/kWh) and PV injection remuneration (0.6€/kWh – high gross market energy price) were assumed. Since the main objective of this laboratory test is focused on the behavior of EWH device, no additional uncontrollable load was considered.

Fig. 2a presents the EWH normal consumption as well as the forecasted PV generation. As shown in the figure, in the normal consumption mode, the appliance switches on after the hot water usage periods (7:45, 17:30 and 21:15). In contrast, in scheduling mode – Fig. 2b – the early morning consumption is moved to the hours when the PV generation is higher (*i.e.*, between 11:00 and 13:00).

Fig. 3 illustrates the difference between the temperatures associated with normal and scheduled consumption. In the normal consumption mode the temperature is kept around the regular setpoint value of 55°C. However, in the scheduling mode, the EWH preserves a low temperature after the first hot water usage, “waiting” for the local PV generation. When the PV installation starts to inject power in the grid, the EWH device switches on until it reaches the upper bound temperature limit. The thermal energy stored in the tank during the PV injection time avoids significant additional consumption to accomplish with the hot water usages in the evening.

Fig.2a. Normal EWH consumption.

V. CASE STUDY

In this section, the optimization method presented above is used to simulate the optimal scheduling of a population of 100 EWH devices comprising different characteristics. Table II summarizes the minimum and maximum values of the thermal and electric characteristics of the EWH population as well as the ambient and water inlet temperatures assumed. Fig. 5 depicts the uncontrollable load diagrams forecasted by each HEMS of the 100 residential consumers. The total hot water usage (in litres) of the consumers are shown in Fig. 6. As illustrated in the figure, the hot water demand is concentrated in the morning and evening periods. The energy and feed in remuneration as well as forecasted PV generation presented in the previous section (fig. 2) are assumed in this case study.

Fig. 2b. EWH consumption with optimal scheduling.

Fig. 3. Normal and scheduling consumption temperatures.

D. Temperature Evaluation

In order to validate the methodology that enables the automatic learning of thermal parameters, the real temperature inside the water tank was evaluated. On/off signals were sent to the Bosch smart appliance during the day in order to accomplish with the consumption profile obtained from the optimal scheduling (fig. 2b). Simultaneously, real temperature measurements were frequently collected, namely in the critical periods (*e.g.*, after and before a hot water usage).

Fig. 4 presents the comparison between the estimated temperature associated with the optimal consumption profile and the real temperature obtained. The comparison shows that, in general, the real temperature losses inside the water tank are higher than the estimated temperature, which means that the thermal admittance coefficient should be larger. However, this imprecise estimation of the thermal loss coefficient does not have an impact on the end-user comfort. In fact, immediately before the hot water usages the water was near the set-point comfort temperature.

Fig. 4. Scheduling temperatures: actual and estimated.

Table II. Electric characteristics of the EWH population.

	Min	Max
C (kWh/°C)	0.059	0.234
α (kW/°C)	1E-04	2E-03
P_{EWH} (kW)	1.5	2.6
θ_e (°C)	25	
θ_i (°C)	13.5	
Thermostat temp. (°C)	55°C	

Fig. 7 presents the comparison between the normal consumption of the appliances (dashed line) and the scheduled demand profile obtained by the self-consumption optimization method considering a time step of 15 minutes. The normal consumption follows the hot water usages of the consumers, *i.e.*, the electric consumption of EWH population increases in the morning and evening periods. In fact, immediately after a the temperature decrease due to a hot water usage, the heating devices switch on in order to keep the temperature at the set-point levels.

In the optimal scheduling of the appliances, the electricity demand is lower in the early morning and evening periods. Similarly to the Bosch water heating device in the laboratory test case, the consumption is “moved” to the PV injection periods. However, the peak of the consumption and the peak of solar irradiance do not happen at the same time. Indeed, at 13:00, the peak of the uncontrollable load also occurs, decreasing the difference between the generation and demand at the local level. Indeed, a peak of local PV generation does not mean an increase of the need for self-consumption through controllable devices. Therefore, the EWH consumption is moved to the subsequent periods, when a small decrease of uncontrollable load occurs in the majority of residential buildings. Furthermore, by postponing the consumption to the afternoon hours, the EWH can store significant thermal energy to accomplish with the hot water needs in the evening with less thermal losses. Even so, a smaller peak consumption occurs at the end of the day in order to bring the temperatures back to the set point levels

The consumption peaks shown in Fig. 7 happen because the same PV generation profile was used for all the residential buildings. Moreover, the scheduling of the appliances was not performed at the system level. In fact, self-consumption relies on local HEMS optimization, which may lead to similarities

regarding optimal scheduling solutions. Finally, it is important to stress that these peaks in EWH consumption do correspond to actual peak in the system demand, since they occur to compensate the local generation.

Fig.5. Baseline Consumption (100 HEMS).

Fig.6. Hot water demand (100 HEMS).

Fig.7. EWH consumption with optimal scheduling.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a methodology to perform optimal scheduling of EWH devices to maximize self-consumption at the HEMS level for the day-ahead. This methodology includes a method to allow automatic learning of EWH thermal parameters as well as a multi-period optimization model.

A laboratory test using a Bosch EWH allowed evaluating the performance of the methodology in real conditions as well

as the potential impact on the end-user. A case study comprising 100 EWH devices was also performed in order to show the aggregate behavior of scheduled appliances enabling self-consumption.

In the future, an intra-day appliances' control algorithm should be implemented to allow modifications in the original EWH scheduling profile in order to face situations of unexpected changes in solar irradiance, hot water demand and uncontrollable load.

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